

WORKING ON ADJUNCTIONS THAT MAKE PERSONAL OBJECT PLACE NOUNS IN PRIMARY GRADES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8194827>

ABSTRACT: In this article, the work on adverbs forming personal, thing, place nouns in elementary grades is discussed. It contains information about teaching this subject to elementary school students, teaching it on the basis of various methods, facilitated by various examples on the subject.

KEY WORDS: lexical meaning, grammatical construction, affixation, composition, semantic method, methodological approach, morphological device

INTRODUCTION

In elementary grades, work on personal, object, place, nouns, formative adverbs, ways and means of teaching Uzbek to students, mastering the mother tongue, that is, study speech, reading and writing, grammar and spelling is the science of acquisition. Based on the educational and educational tasks set before the school, the methodology determines the tasks and content of teaching the mother tongue, examines the process of education, determines the laws of this process and the scientifically based system of teaching methods.

We should start reforming the education sector from the foundation, that is, from the primary classes. Special attention should be paid to the teaching of nouns from independent word groups, a topic that is often encountered in primary classes of mother tongue classes.

MAIN PART

The linguistic basis of the methodology of working on word groups is the division of words into different groups according to lexical-grammatical, morphological and syntactic signs - the science of word groups.

When dividing words into lexical-grammatical categories, there are three signs:

- 1) lexical meaning (generalized meanings of what it represents, i.e. person, thing, action or state, sign, etc.),
- 2) morphological (system of different forms of the word) and
- 3) is based on syntactic (the syntactic function of various morphological forms) signs.

Therefore, work on word groups should be focused on students' understanding of the generalized meanings of words in a certain group, the role of people as a means of communication.

First of all, when working on adverbs that form personal object locative nouns, it is necessary to show students what adverbs are, to explain their meaning, methodological, stylistic, morphological devices, with examples based on new pedagogical technology. It can be explained using the affixation method, the composition method, the semantic method, and the abbreviation method.

Affixes that form personal nouns: -chi: serunum affixes that form nouns from nouns, adjectives, numbers and actions: ov+chi, ish+chi, excellent+chi, lie+chi, two+chi, fight+chi, o'quv+chi

These nouns form several nested groups according to their common meaning: 1) nouns of persons engaged in professions and specialties: worker, oilman, athlete, singer, carpenter, accountant, tinkerer, linguist; 2) nouns of the person participating in the action and event understood from the base: warrior, rebel, hasharchi; 3) the name of a person involved in an action and event understood from the base: republican, defender, informer, etc. are among them.

The suffix -chi is synonymous with some noun-formers. That's why the root words with which they are added have a synonymous relationship: cattle + chi-charva + dor, komak + chi-komak + dosh, mehnat + chi-mehnata + kash, til + chi-til + scholar. This affix is cognate with the preposition -chi, meaning question, surprise, and reinforcement.

-dosh: a noun with the meaning of togetherness, partnership, commonality is made from a noun: compatriot, contemporary, comrade, confidant. This affix sometimes has the meaning of the Tajik prepositional adverb: kasbdosh-kakash, interlocutor-interlocutor.

-kash: makes the nouns of profession and characteristic from the noun: cartman, laborer, penman. This affix is cognate with the adjectival suffix -kash. Compare: mean, heartless, painful.

-bon: a noun is used to form the noun of a person who takes care of something: gardener, shepherd\shepherd, gatekeeper.

-boz: something that is understood from the base of the noun, which makes the noun engaged in training: goalkeeper, pigeon hunter, trickster, swordsman.

-paz: the person who cooks what the noun means, makes the noun: chef, somsapaz, kabobpaz.

Affixes forming nouns of things, weapons, units of measure. This group of noun-formers mainly joins the root of the verb and makes nouns that are the result of an action, an action, a situation. They include: -k (ik /-ak, -uk), -q (-iq, -aq): comb, fence, piece, call, win, sickle, bed. -gi\ -ki\ -qi\ -g'i\ -g'u: broom, instrument, instrument, choppi, yeast, dropper. -gich \-kich\ -kich\ -gich: ruler, scraper, clamp, eraser. -m, -im, -um: a bundle, a pack, a pick, a pick; sip -ma: button, tissue, fold, float, fever, savings.

Affixes forming place nouns. Basically, it forms nouns related to the place of existence of the thing understood from the lexical meaning of the noun:

-loq (-lov): stony place, sandy place, meadow, meadow. -room: kitchen, photo room, ice room.

-time: residence, rest area, playground.

The system of studying the topic "Noun" is a goal-oriented process, in which the generalized meaning and grammatical signs of this word group are studied in a clear sequence, in a scientifically based connection with each other, as well as from the noun in speech. The exercises performed in order to form the skills of correct use and correct writing are gradually becoming more complicated.

The characteristics of the noun as a language phenomenon, the tasks of learning it, taking into account the age characteristics of the students, the amount of material for each class and the consistency of their learning are defined. The tasks of learning a horse in elementary grades are as follows:

- 1) forming the grammatical concept of "noun";

2) who? What are the nouns that are the answer to the question? to develop the skill of distinguishing nouns that are the answer to a question (denoting a thing, an animal, an animal, etc.);

3) formation of the skill of writing people's surnames, first names, patronymics, names of animals and geographical names with capital letters;

4) introducing the number of nouns (singular and plural nouns);

5) formation of the skill of correct use of nouns with possessive suffixes;

6) formation of skills about the classification of nouns by agreement and the writing of agreement suffixes;

7) to enrich students' vocabulary with new nouns and develop the ability to use them clearly and appropriately in speech;

8) to know how to analyze, compare and generalize words.

CONCLUSION

Each of these tasks is solved not separately, but in relation to each other. At the same time, more importance is given to solving a task that must be performed at a certain stage of learning the "Horse" topic. For example, in grades I-II, the signs of a noun (what it means, questions) are studied as a word group, and in grade III, a term is given to a noun, and importance is attached to mastering its use in the singular and plural. In the IV class, attention is paid to the study of the use of nouns with possessive suffixes, their classification with agreements, and the writing of agreement suffixes.

The task of developing students' speech and thinking is solved at all stages of learning the subject. The whole process of studying grammatical material and forming orthographic skills is focused on enriching students' vocabulary, developing connected speech skills and thinking skills.

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